

THE SCIENTIST WHO FOUNDED THE HERIT SCHOOL

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named Kamoliddin behzod.*

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Abstract: The article discusses the role of Kamoliddin Bekhzod, a talented artist of his time, a unique talent in the culture of the East and West, as well as his contribution to the development of world civilization.

Key words: Culture, art, painting, miniature, Herat school, artist.

Attention is paid to the development of measures for the development of art studies, musicology, cultural studies and other scientific directions in the field of cultural activity in today's modernizing Uzbekistan, improvement of training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel in higher education organizations and scientific-research institutions. It was also reflected in the law. Modernizing Uzbekistan cannot be imagined without the philosophical legacy of Middle Ages Eastern thinkers. The history of the Middle Ages of the East shows that the incomparable rise in the fields of culture and education, medicine, literature, art and architecture, the creation of scientific schools, the emergence and coming of age of a new wave of talented generations are still on the minds of the world community. Most of them are included in the UNESCO Cultural Heritage List. Manuscripts of medieval scholars and thinkers of the East are stored in the gold funds of libraries in Europe and Asia, Great Britain, Germany, Spain, Russia, France, Egypt, India, China, Iran and many other countries. This is a priceless treasure, a source of wisdom and knowledge for new generations, and, if necessary, an excellent material for new discoveries.

In general, today our scholars of culture and art are paying special attention to the study of the spiritual culture of the East and the West, and to clarifying the theoretical problems of independence. It is also worth saying that the scientific

research works and their results in this field meet the requirements of the present time. Viewing the spiritual culture of the East and the West as a system of universal human values, using the historical heritage and national cultural experience of other countries in this regard, connecting scientific research in this field with the most important tasks facing Uzbekistan are important tasks for art historians. After all, our ancient and beautiful land was one of the cradles of not only Eastern, but also world civilization. Great people, scholars, politicians and generals have emerged from this blessed land, and the services of the great scholars who were born and matured in our motherland were incomparable in raising the worldly and religious sciences, especially the knowledge related to the development of science, to the highest level in history.

Miniature art, calligraphy (kitobot), developed in Movarounnahr and Khorasan in the X-XI centuries, reached a high stage of maturity in the XIV-XV centuries. This period is associated with the names of Amir Temur and the Timurid kings Shahrukh, Ulug'bek, Husayn Boykara, and among other fields, it became the center of the school of painting, which has its own direction of content, artistic style, traditions, and rules of aesthetic law. During this period, the miniature art, which has its own ancient history, developed, and Movarounnahr, Arab, Iranian Turkish, Azerbaijani and Indian schools of miniatures were created. In the second half of the 15th century, the Herat Miniature School was established in Hossein Boykara Palace in Herat under the auspices of Alisher Navoi, founded by Kamaluddin Behzad and his teachers Mirak Naqqosh Khurasani, Pir Cayyid Tabrizi. We know that Alisher Navoi had a great contribution to the cultural development of Herat. "The great master (Behzod) achieved his famous painting thanks to the blessing and care of Amir Nizamiddin Alisher," writes historian Khondamir (1. 4.)

According to the sources, Kamoliddin Behzod with his amazing art of painting "Moniy soni" (the second Moni) became such a skilled artist in a short period of time that in terms of the elegance of his paintings and the bright color of his miniatures, he occupies a special place in the visual art of the East, and he is the

"Raphael of the East" will be entitled to receive such names. His portraits, especially those of Alisher Navoi, Sultan Husayn and Shaibani Khan, have gained immense fame. About an event that shows the influence of Kamaluddin Behzad's artistic skills and works, Vasifi's book "Badayi ul-Waqe" describes in detail: One day, Behzad brought a newly made picture to Navoi: a wonderful garden, trees, birds on the branches of trees, flowers blooming in the ditches. waters. The bright Alisher Navoi in the garden. He was leaning on a cane with one hand, a plate in the other hand, gold on the plate. People of science, art and literature surround Navoi. It is as if Navoi is happy with their creative work and wants to sprinkle gold on their heads... Enjoying the photo, Navoi recites a verse with the following content:

A painter, a wonderful morning artist,

It's good time, it's good time

(Meaning: Painter, you have painted a wonderful page, have a good time, because you made us happy.). (":2.6.)

If we study Kamoliddin Behzod's work from today's point of view, we can clearly say that his works stand alongside the works of the great artists of the West. Behzod's work is in line with the creative traditions of great European artists. The socio-aesthetic ideals, aspirations and concepts of the peoples of the Middle East are vividly expressed in Behzod's works. Behzod's work, which is the pinnacle of Eastern fine art, became a school of painting in its time, and many painters were trained in this school.

The portrait of Husayn Boygaro, created by Kamoliddin Behzod, raised the artist's creativity to a higher level. In its time, this portrait made not only Behzod, but also the king of Khorasan, Sultan Husayn Mirza Boykara, known and famous. The original portrait of Sultan Husayn Boykara depicted in royal dress is kept in the personal collection of the Swedish art historian F.R. Martin. F. Martin Behzod was very interested in miniature art and wrote a lot about it. Musavvir created "Alisher Navoi", "Abdurahman Jami", "Muhammad Shaibani Khan" and several other portrait works.

His contemporary, the great historian Khondamir, who realized that Kamoliddin Behzad's work was brilliant and immortal, was amazed by his talent and wrote in his work "Habib us-siyar": "His painter's brush, similar to Moni's brush, makes the painters of the world forget, and his wonderful and miraculous fingers are Adam. It eclipses the works of all the painters among the descendants of Ato. This artist, who embodies the pure truth, is a wonder of our time, and is currently receiving the blessings of the rulers of the whole world. Such assessment given to Kamoliddin Behzod, a master artist of his time and possessor of extremely unique abilities, has not lost its importance even today. At this point, if we turn to another historical source, it is time to reject the baseless conclusions of historians (in the works of L.A. Ivanov, N.V. Doyakonov) written before our independence that there was no miniature school in Central Asia in the 14th-15th centuries. We think that the time when Kamoliddin Behzod lived will provide the answer to such difficult questions. Qazi Ahmed, who wrote a treatise on painters during the time when Kamoliddin Behzad lived, writes: "Behzod became such a skilled painter in a short period of time that since the appearance of color images, there was no one equal to him among artists in this field" (2.5.).

As a general conclusion, during the years of Independence, great progress was made in terms of national-spiritual revival. National-spiritual revival is a process that involves, first of all, assimilation of national-spiritual heritage and restoration of historical memory. In this regard, the contributions of our great spiritual leaders and scholars to the development of world science, such as Kamoliddin Behzod, have been thoroughly studied and widely promoted. In the works created by Behzod, the main goal is to know the divine and worldly world on the basis of beauty, to respond to the trends and moods of the times on the basis of beauty. There are many unexplored aspects of this great heritage for us. In order to understand the essence of this beauty more deeply, we need to delve into Behzod's works and the ideas presented in them.

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